

nematode. Most of the ufra-prone areas grow broadcast aman (B. aman) rice Apr-Nov, followed by boro rice Nov - Mar. That helps the ufra nematode survive throughout the year.

Repeated cultivation of highly susceptible varieties Kaladhan, Dudhomona, and Kaligacha has contributed to the development of ufra. These varieties also act as sources of secondary and tertiary inocula.

About 60-70% of the areas, covering about 200,000 ha, was infested.

Digha variety was found to be resistant in one zone, probably because it escaped the disease because of its early maturity. Khalni was moderately resistant. In the two other zones, local B. aman varieties Rayanda (Rayada) and Keora were resistant. Other minor diseases observed during the survey are given in the table. □

Disease distribution in deepwater rice areas of Bangladesh, with existing cropping pattern and varieties cultivated. Bangladesh, 1986.

Zones of Bangladesh	Cropping pattern ^a	Varieties cultivated	Diseased ^b		Ufra infestation (%)	Varieties resistant to ufra ^c
			Major	Minor		
Pabna	BA or rabi/boro	Sharshari, Boron, Dhaldhigha, Bhawalia	ShB (only in one location)	BB, B1, BS, ShR	—	—
Barisal	BA or TA/rabi/ boro	Chikon, Mota, Pajam ^d , Dudhmona ^d , Gorcha, Asfal ^d , Khalni, Digha, BR11, IR5, Joia ^d	Ufra	BB, B1, LSc, ShR, ShB	40-50%	Digha (R) Khalni (MR)
Faridpur Khulna	BA or rabi/ boro	Grkajal ^d , Kaladhad Ufra, Digha ^d , Joia ^d , Khaiya motor ^d , Rayanda, Marchan	Ufra	BS, ShR, B1	60-70%	Rayanda (R)
Sylhet	BA or rabi/ fallow	Karkati, Badal, Bazail, Biron	—	ShR, BB	—	—
Comilla Noakhali	BA or rabi/ boro	Kaligacha ^d , Barwa ^d , Keora, Aman, Hirbain	Ufra	ShR	80-90%	Keora (R)

^aBA = broadcast aman, TA = transplanted aman. ^bBB = bacterial blight, B1 = blast, BS = brown spot, ShR = sheath rot, ShB = sheath blight, LSc = leaf scald. ^cR = resistant, MR = moderately resistant. ^dHighly susceptible to ufra.

Weed hosts of ragged stunt virus (RSV)

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We collected young weed plants of different species commonly found in ricefields and transplanted them individually in pots. Each plant was exposed to 50 RSV-viruliferous brown planthopper (BPH) for 2 d.

One month after inoculation, the 2 youngest leaves of each plant were homogenized with 2 times (by weight) 0.02 M PBS-Tween. Extracts were tested in ELISA for the presence of RSV antigen. Extracts of uninoculated weed plants served as the control. Absorbance values at 405 nm of test extracts above 2 times mean absorbance value of control extracts were considered positive.

Echinochloa glabrescens, *Eleusine indica*, *Monochoria vaginalis*, and *Paspalum distichum* gave positive ELISA; *Commelina benghalensis*, *Echinochloa colona*, *Echinochloa crus-galli*, *Ischaemum rugosum*, and *Ludwigia octovalvis* negative (see table). That result indicates that some weed

Detection of RSV by ELISA in weeds inoculated with RSV.

Weed species	Inoculated samples (no.)	Infected samples (no.)	Average absorbance at 405 nm ^a	
			Infected	Control
<i>Echinochloa glabrescens</i>	23	4	0.42	0.19
<i>Eleusine indica</i>	33	3	0.90	0.02
<i>Monochoria vaginalis</i>	35	10	0.58	0.07
<i>Paspalum distichum</i>	23	6	0.32	0.09

^aValue above 2 × absorbance value of control considered positive.

species can be hosts of RSV.

BPH nymphs given a 1.5-d acquisition access on some of the plants

gave positive ELISA. Nymphs fed on healthy rice seedlings for 8 d, then tested for infectivity, did not transmit RSV. □

Frequency and timing of insecticide application to control rice tungro virus (RTV)

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When vector populations are high, using insecticides to control RTV infection in moderately resistant and susceptible cultivars requires increasing the number of applications. More precise timing of insecticide application could reduce the number of applications needed.

We conducted two trials during the 1986 wet season to test insecticide timing and application frequency. IR64 (resistant) and TN1 (susceptible to green leafhopper and RTV) were planted in 5 × 7-m plots with 4 replications. The seedbeds were covered by mesh to prevent early RTV infection. In the first trial, cypermethrin (0.05 kg ai/ha) and monocrotophos (0.4 kg ai/ha) were applied 4 times at 10-d intervals starting at 1, 5, or 10 d after transplanting (DT). RTV infected hills were recorded at 60 DT.